

ETH zürich

Solar Pasteurization for Anaerobic Digestion Sludge

Author: Tim-Luân Grimont

Supervisors: Prof. Elizabeth Tilley

Dr. Jakub Tkaczuk

Tutor: Prof. Eleni Chatzi

31st of September 2024

Acknowledgements

Thanks to Mobile Alert Toilets and Toilets for All for their support.

Thanks to the staff and students at Raini Primary School for their curiosity, understanding, and their continuous inputs to the solar pasteurizer.

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements	2
Abstract	5
1 Introduction	6
1.1 Fecal Pathogens	6
1.2 Anaerobic Digestion	6
1.3 Pasteurization	7
1.4 Solar Pasteurization	9
1.5 Justification and Research Goals	10
2 Methods	11
2.1 Site selection	11
2.2 Installation	12
2.2.1 Solar Water Heater	12
2.2.2 Piping	13
2.3 Temperature Control	13
2.3.1 Purpose	13
2.3.2 Riser Pipe	14
2.3.3 Thermostat Valve	15
2.4 Heat Exchanger	15
2.4.1 Purpose	15
2.4.2 Concept	16
2.5 Convection Loop	16
2.5.1 Purpose	16
2.6 Sampling and Laboratory Analysis	17
2.7 Sensors	18
2.7.1 Thermocouples	18
2.7.2 Luxmeter	18
2.8 Python Model Building and Fitting	19
2.8.1 Solar Sludge Heater	19
2.8.2 Solar Pasteurizer	20
2.9 Python Model Application	22
2.9.1 Weather Data	22
2.9.2 Model Analysis	23

3	Results and Discussion	24
3.1	E.coli Concentration	24
3.2	Impact of the Convection Loop	25
3.2.1	Effectiveness	25
3.2.2	Behavior Concerns - Thermostat valve	26
3.3	System Cost	27
3.4	Model Results	27
3.4.1	Volume of Pasteurized Flow	27
3.4.2	Holding Time	28
3.4.3	Parameter Analysis	29
3.4.4	Operation under Ideal Parameters	32
3.4.5	Limitations of the Model	33
3.5	Degradation of Components	34
3.6	Improved Solar Pasteurizer	35
4	Conclusions and Recommendations	38
	Bibliography	39
	Annex	41
	Annex 1	41
	Annex 2	42
	Annex 3	44

Abstract

Anaerobic digestion is a waste-valorization process that converts human waste into biogas and fecal sludge as a by-product. The resulting sludge contains fecal matter and pathogens responsible for a variety of diseases, with diarrhea being particularly prevalent in Sub-Saharan Africa. To reduce the risk of infection from the waste stream, this sludge must be sanitized before disposal.

Solar pasteurization is a sanitation technology that utilizes solar energy to heat sludge beyond the survival threshold of pathogens. Effective pasteurization requires both high temperatures and sufficient holding time to eliminate microorganisms. This study explores the adaptation of an off-the-shelf solar water heater, available in Kenya, to pasteurize anaerobic digester sludge derived from human waste.

The pasteurizer operates with a convection loop to evenly distribute temperatures within the system, a heat exchanger to recover heat from the treated sludge, and a thermostatic valve set to 78 °C to regulate the temperature at which the sludge exits the system. During fieldwork in Nairobi, conducted in the winter months with low solar irradiance, the valve's temperature setpoint was not reached, preventing the collection of fully processed sludge samples. However, by analyzing samples from both the anaerobic digester and the main tank of the pasteurizer, it was found that the system could achieve low-temperature pasteurization, resulting in a 99 % reduction in *E. coli* concentrations.

A basic Python model was developed to simulate pasteurizer operation using the temperature and solar irradiance data collected in Nairobi. Simulations were also conducted using irradiance data from Narok and Homa Bay, focusing on the effects of three control parameters: the thermostatic valve setpoint, solar collector area, and heat exchanger efficiency. From this analysis, it was determined that the solar collector area and the thermostatic valve setpoint are the most effective levers for improving system performance. Increasing the collector area enhances productivity (i.e., the volume of sludge processed), while raising the temperature setpoint of the thermostatic valve extends the holding time, which is crucial for thorough pasteurization. However, productivity and holding time are inversely proportional – increasing one typically reduces the other. What makes these two parameters effective is that they allow for improving one target metric without severely compromising the other, making them ideal control levers for optimizing system performance.

After one month of operation, maintenance revealed significant corrosion of the sacrificial anode inside the main tank. To prevent further degradation of components from sludge exposure, a two-cycle heating system is proposed, where water would act as the working and heating fluid for sludge pasteurization. When implemented in the right location, a solar pasteurizer system could offer improved sanitation at a lower cost and with less space required than conventional post-treatment methods.

1 Introduction

1.1 Fecal Pathogens

Human excreta (urine and feces) serve as a vehicle for a wide range of debilitating diseases. The impact of these infections on individuals includes malnutrition, diarrhea, stunted growth, disability, and even death. At the societal level, at-risk populations endure lower educational attainment, poor living conditions, and the threat of epidemic outbreaks. Consequently, disease and poverty are perpetuated, with inadequate waste management identified as one of the root causes of these issues.

Diarrheal disease is the most prevalent infection resulting from fecal pathogens and is a leading cause of child mortality and morbidity worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), children under three years old in low-income countries experience an average of three episodes of diarrhea annually. The most common pathogens responsible for diarrhea include rotavirus, norovirus, adenovirus, and astrovirus, all of which can be transmitted through feces-contaminated water. Helminths, another significant cause of morbidity, affect approximately 1.5 billion people and are transmitted through soils contaminated with fecal matter, particularly in regions where fecal sludge is used for agricultural irrigation.

Currently, over 1.5 billion people lack access to basic sanitation services, which are defined as improved sanitation facilities that are not shared with other households (WHO/UNICEF Joint Programme for Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene (JMP), 2023). Improved sanitation facilities encompass flush toilets connected to piped sewer systems, pit latrines, and composting toilets.

The aim of sanitation systems is to interrupt the transmission cycles of pathogens by effectively treating human waste from the moment it is excreted, during disposal, and until it has been safely discharged.

1.2 Anaerobic Digestion

Despite the dangers associated with human waste, our excreta can also be viewed as a valuable resource. Nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus, along with biogas produced from fecal decomposition, can be harnessed and utilized by specialized sanitation facilities.

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a waste-valorization process primarily used for organic waste, wherein the waste is processed for several days by two types of anaerobic organisms. The output of this process includes biogas, which typically consists of 55-75 % methane (Reith & Wijffels, 2003), making it a viable energy source, and a sludge that is partially sanitized, more

homogeneous, and less odorous, which is routinely used as fertilizer for crops.

In the case study at hand, the feedstock comprises human excreta and flush water. Although the exact ratio is not yet well established, it is estimated that there is a daily input of 50 kg of human excreta and 200 liters of flush water. Additionally, every two weeks, 50 kg of fresh cow dung is fed into the digester to inoculate it with bacteria.

The anaerobic digesters in this study were constructed by Sistema.bio. In this system, human excreta are flushed into a holding tank before flowing gravitationally into balloon digesters, which serve as physical containment vessels for processing over a period of approximately two months. Conventional mesophilic process temperatures are employed (Labatut et al., 2014), as this approach is more stable than its thermophilic counterpart and does not require external heating.

Tubes are attached to the top of the balloon digesters, functioning as conduits for the biogas produced. The biogas is directed through a water trap and a hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) filter before reaching the cooking stove in the school kitchen.

The effectiveness of AD as a sanitization method, particularly regarding measures such as the sterility assurance level (SAL), remains an open research question. AD sludge still contains pathogens, including traces of *E. coli*, which raises health concerns associated with its use in agriculture or discharge in urban environments (Owamah et al., 2014; Winker et al., 2009).

1.3 Pasteurization

Pasteurization is a sanitation technique that employs high temperatures combined with a specific holding time to effectively kill pathogens. By increasing the application temperature, the required duration of treatment can be significantly reduced.

Feachem et al., (1981) formalized the requirements for pasteurization of fecal pathogens by defining a "safety zone" of time-temperature combinations necessary for pathogen inactivation.

Figure 1. 1 Time-temperature curves for inactivation of at least 90 % of microorganisms

In a more recent study, Espinosa et al., (2020) revised the safety zone defined by Feachem et. al using updated information on various pathogen inactivation curves. The result is a more stringent heat treatment required to achieve the same levels of pathogen inactivation, as illustrated in Figure 1. 1. This revised safety zone establishes thresholds for at least 90 % reduction and 99.9 % reduction for all pathogens. Table 1. 1 presents the temperature and holding time combinations associated with both Feachem et al.’s original safety zone and the newly revised zones.

Table 1. 1 Temperature-time combinations needed for different levels of pathogen inactivation

Temperature (°C)	Time [min] 1981 safety zone	Time [min] zone of 90 % reduction	Time [min] zone of 99.9 % reduction
64	35	369	7973
68	13	170	4530
72	6	79	2718
76	6	71	1652
80	6	65	1044

These temperature-time combinations can serve as guidelines for the design of a pasteurization system. However, validation of such a system can be achieved through more direct methods of fecal bacteria detection. *Escherichia coli* is a bacterium that resides in the intestines of vertebrates and is currently regarded as the best fecal indicator bacterium. Although the vast majority of E.coli types are harmless, its concentration is often used as a proxy for evaluating the presence of other fecal pathogens, thereby verifying the effectiveness of a pasteurization process. E.coli concentrations are measured in colony-forming units per volume of the tested sample (cfu/mL), where colony-forming units indicate the number of bacterial cells that remain viable enough to proliferate. When comparing E.coli concentrations before and after pasteurization, the decrease

in cfu/mL is expressed as a number of log reductions, corresponding to the factor of ten by which the number of colonies has been reduced.

A critical concern in designing a sanitation system is the risk of regrowth and recontamination in the post-processing phase. Recontamination can occur when the processed and unprocessed components of a sanitation system are not adequately separated, or when processed effluent comes into contact with other sources of fecal pathogens due to issues such as leaks or unhygienic handling. Regrowth can happen through three processes: reactivation from a viable but non-culturable state, repair of photo-induced DNA damage, and reproduction of bacteria that survive disinfection. This risk can be mitigated by avoiding conditions that favor bacterial growth in the post-pasteurization environment, such as high humidity (Wang et al., 2021).

1.4 Solar Pasteurization

Pasteurization using solar irradiance as a heat source has been studied extensively to provide safe drinking water to impoverished communities.

Carielo da Silva et al. (2016) conducted decontamination of water using a flat plate solar collector with a 2 m² aperture area and a photovoltaic module to control the system. Their tests examined temperatures ranging from 55 °C to 85 °C, resulting in a maximum production of 45 l/day. They found that the productivity of the pasteurizer is directly proportional to the accumulated irradiation and emphasized the necessity of a heat exchanger to enhance productivity.

Dobrowsky et al., (2015) utilized a commercial solar heater equipped with evacuated tube solar collectors to pasteurize water. At temperatures exceeding 72 °C, effective reductions in E.coli and total coliform concentrations were achieved. However, PCR analysis still detected *Yersinia* species (spp.), *Legionella* spp., and *Pseudomonas* spp., underscoring the importance of rigorous bacteriological analysis to validate sanitation technologies.

Duff & Hodgson, (2005a) successfully implemented a density-driven system that operates without a thermostatic valve, heating water up to 78 °C.

The effluent targeted for pasteurization in this study contains a significantly higher concentration of fecal matter than the inputs analyzed in the aforementioned studies. Moreover, the objective is not to convert this effluent into safe drinking water. Consequently, while the sanitation level requirements may not be as stringent due to the lack of direct ingestion, the conditions necessary to achieve comparable levels of sanitation, as demonstrated in previous research, are indeed more demanding.

1.5 Justification and Research Goals

The goal of this study is to mitigate the risks of disease transmission by fecal pathogens present in the sludge produced by human excreta-fed AD, through the development of a solar-powered pasteurization system. This system is designed for deployment in regions of Sub-Saharan Africa where access to electricity is limited, but solar resources are abundant.

The study aims to determine the daily volume of sludge that can be pasteurized per square meter of solar collector, as well as the corresponding pasteurization temperatures and holding times that can be achieved. To validate the system's effectiveness, the study will assess the number of log reductions in E.coli achieved through pasteurization.

In addition, the study will evaluate the impact of sludge exposure on system components and provide recommendations for minimizing degradation, if necessary. Finally, the economic viability of the system will be assessed based on its associated costs.

2 Methods

2.1 Site selection

Figure 2. 1 Map of Nairobi with the pinned position of Raini Primary School

The study was conducted at Raini Primary School in Kiambu County, Kenya. This government school, situated within a tea plantation, serves a student population of 253 boys and 224 girls.

Raini Primary School has partnered with Mobile Alert Toilets to install improved sanitation facilities, which are connected to a Sistema.bio AD system. The existing infrastructure provides a consistent supply of effluent sludge, making the school an ideal testing site for the solar pasteurization system.

Figure 2. 2 Toilet blocks at Raini

During the two months of field work (May and June 2024), the new boys' toilet block (blue roof in Figure 2. 2) was under construction. Thus, the AD was fed by the girls' toilet block (red roof

in Figure 2. 2), with 200 liters of water being used daily to flush the human waste into the AD system. The flushwater tank is also visible on the far right of Figure 2. 2.

Figure 2. 3a. (left) AD and b. (right) Gravel filtration bed.

The AD consists of two balloon digesters arranged in series (Figure 2. 3a.); the first has a volume 6 m^3 , the second has a volume 20 m^3 . Tubing from the top of these digesters channels biogas to H_2S scrubbers, which then direct it to the school kitchen stove.

Previously, the post-treatment solution for the effluent sludge involved a gravel filtration bed. Effluent from the second balloon digester was routed into the filtration bed via a PVC pipe outlet. After filtration, a sewage canal carried the effluent to an old pit latrine located next to a maize field (visible in the back of Figure 2. 3b.).

The entire system is built on a downhill incline, allowing for gravitational pumping of the effluent.

2.2 Installation

2.2.1 Solar Water Heater

For simplicity and to ensure future scalability, the least expensive solar water heater was selected for this study, with the biodigester effluent being used directly as the working fluid.

The chosen model is the Seven Stars Solar 150-litre capacity vacuum tube heater (see Annex 2). This system includes a mounting frame for inclination, a main tank, 15 vacuum-insulated tubes, and a sacrificial anode rod. The secondary tank and smart control panel were not utilized in this installation.

Figure 2. 4a. (left) and b. (right) Current solar pasteurizer prototype.

Figure 2. 4a. and b. show the current system, beginning at the PVC outlet of the biodigester. The system incorporates Heat Exchanger, Convection Loop, and Thermostat Valve for temperature control.

2.2.2 Piping

All piping elements were constructed using Polypropylene Random Copolymer (PPR) components, a well-established and readily available piping technology in Nairobi and across Kenya. PPR was chosen for its ease of assembly and configuration, making it a practical option for the system.

The connection of two pipe elements was achieved through fusion welding. This process involves using a specialized welding machine to melt the contact areas at 260 °C, ensuring a secure and durable bond.

2.3 Temperature Control

2.3.1 Purpose

The temperature control component plays a crucial role in ensuring the pasteurization process is effective. Positioned at the outlet of the pasteurizer, it regulates the flow of effluent, allowing only the sludge that has reached the designated pasteurization temperature to exit the system. This guarantees that the treated effluent meets the necessary thermal requirements for pathogen inactivation.

2.3.2 Riser Pipe

Figure 2. 5 Riser pipe

The riser pipe serves as a temperature control mechanism based on the density difference between cold, untreated effluent and hot, pasteurized effluent. For example, a column of water at 20 °C (the lower temperature range of untreated effluent, with a density of 998.2 kg/m³) can support a column of water at 70 °C (with a density of 977 kg/m³) that is 1.0215 times taller. Given that the PVC outlet of the AD is positioned 96.5 cm above the main tank of the pasteurizer, setting the riser pipe at 98.5 cm above the tank should, theoretically, allow effluent to spill out once it reaches 70 °C (see Annex 1).

However, in practice, several factors influence the setting of the riser pipe height. The temperature of the effluent does not rise instantly from 20 °C to 70 °C upon entering the main tank, creating a temperature gradient. Consequently, the riser pipe's height was adjusted experimentally, by varying its length until spillover occurred at approximately 70 °C.

The volume of liquid inside the biodigester balloon is determined by the inflow and outflow of effluent, while the volume of biogas depends on the rate of production and its use in the kitchen. As a result, both the effluent level and internal pressure in the biodigester fluctuate over time.

The riser pipe relies on stable conditions to function effectively. If the internal pressure in the biodigester increases due to excess biogas, it can push effluent out of the riser pipe at a lower temperature than intended. Similarly, rising effluent levels in the biodigester can cause the same issue. This variability makes it difficult to set the correct height for the riser pipe and to ensure it functions properly.

The concept of the riser pipe was borrowed from Duff & Hodgson, (2005a). In their study, the water level was maintained at a constant height using a machine screw, and the system was not hermetically sealed. This design ensured that the internal pressure was always at atmospheric levels, allowing for stable operation. By contrast, in the current system, the pressure inside the

biodigester fluctuates based on biogas production and effluent levels, making it more difficult to control the riser pipe's function effectively.

2.3.3 Thermostat Valve

Figure 2. 6 Integration of the thermostat valve into PPR piping.

The thermostat valve, commonly used in motor vehicle cooling systems, operates by utilizing the heat expansion properties of wax. Its core is filled with wax that has a high thermal expansion coefficient, and the valve is kept closed by a spring. As the engine coolant heats up, the expanding wax eventually reaches a temperature where it overcomes the spring's resistance, forcing the valve to open. This allows the coolant to flow to the radiator once the engine reaches its optimal operating temperature.

This same concept can be adapted for use in a solar pasteurizer. In this application, the valve opens only when the effluent has reached the desired pasteurization temperature. To integrate the thermostat valve into the pasteurizer's piping, as illustrated in Figure 2. 6, a larger diameter PPR pipe (50 mm) was selected to accommodate the size of the valve's primary disc. The edges of two 50 mm PPR components were melted and fused together, with the thermostat valve securely trapped between them.

2.4 Heat Exchanger

2.4.1 Purpose

The heat exchanger is designed to enhance the efficiency of the pasteurizer by reducing the solar energy required to reach the pasteurization temperature. It achieves this by utilizing the heat from the hot, pasteurized effluent to preheat the cold, incoming raw effluent before it enters the solar water heater. This process optimizes energy usage, allowing the system to operate more effectively and ensuring that less solar energy is needed for heating.

2.4.2 Concept

Figure 2. 7 Heat exchanger before being mounted to the solar pasteurizer

A 2-meter counterflow tube-in-shell heat exchanger has been constructed using an inner tube, an outer shell, two T-connectors at each end, and ring seals to close the gaps between the inner tube and the T-connectors.

Achieving a proper seal has proven challenging; however, the most effective method employed has been using a silicone gun. Given the uncertainty regarding the seal's integrity, a decision was made to run the hot effluent through the shell and the cold effluent through the inner tube. This design ensures that, in the event of a leak, only the hot, already pasteurized effluent would escape, rather than the untreated effluent.

2.5 Convection Loop

2.5.1 Purpose

Figure 2. 8a. (left) convection pipe intake and b. (right) exit; on the riser pipe

The convection pipe facilitates circulation between the main tank and the PPR outlet. It extends from the riser pipe, positioned above the main tank, and returns to the inlet of the solar water heater. This design promotes the homogenization of the sludge temperature, ensuring consistent heating throughout the system.

For optimal performance, the convection loop must be elevated a few centimeters above the top of the main tank. Additionally, the inlet of the convection loop should be positioned significantly higher than its outlet to ensure proper flow direction.

2.6 Sampling and Laboratory Analysis

Figure 2. 9 System diagram with sampling locations denoted by sample number

There are 5 sample types that can be collected on the system, and they can be differentiated by the location at which they are collected as seen in green boxes in Figure 2. 9.

- 1) Raw Effluent - collected at the tap installed directly next to the AD balloon outlet.
- 2) Semi-Treated Effluent - collected directly from the main tank by opening a PPR pipe connection.
- 3) Fully-Treated Effluent - collected from a tap right after the thermostat valve.
- 4) Fully-Processed Effluent - collected from the final outlet of the system, after the heat exchanger.
- 5) Fully-Processed Effluent (Leak) - collected from the final outlet of the system, situated after the heat exchanger. However, it is a drip sample due to the thermostat valve not achieving a perfect seal.

Samples are collected using clean bottles and placed in a cooler box while awaiting drop-off at the laboratory. To minimize the risk of contamination, samples are collected in an order that hypothetically ranges from the least amount of E.coli to the most. This means collecting samples in the following sequence: 5 to 1.

The membrane filtration method is used to count the number of cfu/100mL of sample. Before this analysis, a dilution factor is applied based on trial and error from previous samples. The 'Raw Effluent' is diluted by a factor of 200 due to its high E.coli concentrations, while the other samples are diluted by a factor of 10.

2.7 Sensors

Figure 2. 10 System diagram with thermocouple location by number and luxmeter location

2.7.1 Thermocouples

Temperature data is recorded using thermocouples in 4 locations of the system with a sampling time of 10 minutes. These locations can be seen in red boxes in Figure 2. 10.

- 1) Raw Effluent Temperature - located at the outlet of the AD balloon.
- 2) Heat Exchange Temperature - located right after the heat exchanger, it can be used to determine the temperature difference that occurs due to preheating via heat exchanger, and is needed to calculate the efficiency of the heat exchange.
- 3) Main Tank Temperature - located inside a metal sleeve that is inserted into the main tank for the purpose of temperature monitoring. This temperature can inform on how well the solar water heater performs when capturing radiation.
- 4) Outlet Block Temperature - located in the PPR piping right before the temperature control, it is used as an indicator of when the effluent is going to flow out of the system.

The 4 thermocouples are connected to a digital thermometer: SEFRAM 9816B.

2.7.2 Luxmeter

The luxmeter LX-1148SD is positioned on top of the vacuum heating tubes, with the same angle of inclination, seen in the blue circle in Figure 2. 10. It records sample data every 10 minutes.

The unit of measurement for the data is lux. However, an approximate conversion of $0.0079 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2} / \text{lx}$ is applied for sunlight to obtain irradiance.

The luxmeter has a maximum reading of 99999 lux, or $789.9921 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2}$.

2.8 Python Model Building and Fitting

2.8.1 Solar Sludge Heater

A python model for the solar water heater is built using the temperature and light data collected, to simulate the observed behavior.

Initial assumptions are made for the model:

- The main tank temperature is identical to the temperature at the outlet; in other words, the convection loop is functioning properly.
- The heat capacity of the sludge is equal to that of water ($C = 4.186 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{g}\cdot\text{K}}$), and its density is approximated to $1000 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{L}}$.
- The sludge gains heat via the vacuum tubes from solar radiation, which can be pulled from the luxmeter data.
- The sludge loses heat through conduction and convection heat transfer to the surrounding air, with air temperature being approximated by the data from T3 (temperature of the sludge when exiting the balloon digester).

Thereafter, the temperature of the main tank in °C can be modeled by initializing it a starting temperature, and calculating its temperature by 10 minutes increments such that:

$$T_{t+1} = T_t + \Delta T_t^{irr} - \Delta T_t^{con}$$

Equation 2. 1

Where T_{t+1} and T_t are the predicted main tank temperatures in °C at times t and $t + 1$ respectively. ΔT_t^{irr} is the temperature gain in °C due to solar irradiance being converted to heat by the collector at time t . It is calculated with the solar energy incident on the solar collector, which can be found from the luxmeter data, such that:

$$\Delta T_t^{irr} = k \cdot \frac{Irr_t \cdot S}{C \cdot f \cdot M},$$

Equation 2. 2

where Irr_t is the irradiance data from the luxmeter at time t in $\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2}$. f is the sampling frequency in Hertz, S is linked to the main tank capacity and is the surface area of the solar collector in m^2 (see Annex 2), C is the heat capacity of the sludge in $\frac{\text{J}}{\text{g}\cdot\text{K}}$, M is the mass of the sludge inside the main tank in grams, and k is a correctional dimensionless factor that is optimised for. ΔT_t^{con} is the temperature loss in °C due to convective and conductive heat transfer from the main tank to surrounding air at time t :

$$\Delta T_t^{con} = U \cdot A \frac{T_t - T_t^{air}}{C \cdot f \cdot M},$$

Equation 2. 3

where A depends on the main tank capacity and is the surface area where the heat transfer occurs in m^2 (see Annex 2), T_t is the temperature inside the main tank in $^{\circ}C$ at time t , T_t^{air} is the air temperature in $^{\circ}C$ at time t approximated by the data from the thermocouple at the outlet of the AD. U is the overall heat transfer coefficient in $\frac{W}{m^2 \times K}$, and is optimised for.

Figure 2. 11 Temperature simulation using luxmeter data, next to thermocouple data

The factors k from Equation 2. 2 and U from Equation 2. 3 are found using gridsearch to best fit the known temperature curves (blue plot in Figure 2. 11) collected from the main tank in Raini Primary School.

The optimized parameters are $U = 2.414 \frac{W}{m^2 \cdot K}$, and $k = 0.993$, and these parameters yield a simulation $RMSE = 3.928 \text{ }^{\circ}C$. The $RMSE$ – or Root Mean Squared Error – measures the average difference between the model’s predicted values and the actual measured main tank temperature. As expected, k is very close to 1, as the vacuum heating tubes are very efficient at converting incident irradiance into heat.

2.8.2 Solar Pasteurizer

This Python model is then expanded to incorporate pasteurization dynamics and the heat exchanger. To achieve this, additional assumptions and dynamics are defined to capture the behavior of the pasteurizer during operation:

- When the temperature in the main tank reaches the thermostat valve temperature setpoint T^{valve} in $^{\circ}C$, the thermostatic valve opens to let sludge flow out. This means that the temperature does not exceed T^{valve} . After a certain amount of sludge has flowed out and temperature in the main tank has lowered, the valve closes.

- A dimensionless discharge factor x between 0 and 1 is introduced to represent the portion of the main tank capacity that has not been discharged out of the main tank during the time that the valve was open. Consequently, $(1 - x)$ denotes the portion of the main tank that is refilled with incoming preheated effluent. Additionally, the discharge of pasteurized effluent is considered to be instantaneous.
- This preheated effluent flows into the main tank at temperature T^{preh} in °C, which can be determined by introducing heat exchanger efficiency e between 0 and 1. Thus:

$$T^{preh} = T_t^{air} + e \cdot (T^{valve} - T_t^{air}) ,$$

Equation 2. 4

where the air temperature at time t is used as a proxy for the temperature of the cold sludge as it exits the AD.

- Once T^{valve} is reached, the temperature of the main tank is reset to a value T^{new} that represents a mixture of T^{valve} and T^{preh} :

$$T^{new} = x \cdot T^{valve} + (1 - x) \cdot T^{preh}$$

Equation 2. 5

- The amount of effluent the pasteurizer is able to treat V in liters can be found by counting the number of times T^{valve} is reached n :

$$V = n \cdot (1 - x) \cdot MTC$$

Equation 2. 6

Where MTC is the main tank capacity in liters. The sludge yield of the pasteurizer is reported in liters per day per square meter of collector area (liters/day/m²). Given that the vacuum heating tubes are spaced apart, their cumulative area accounts for approximately 60-70 % of the overall collector area (see Annex 2).

- To determine a conservative holding time, a pasteurization temperature T^{past} is established, set at 72 °C. The holding time is then measured based on the duration the sludge remains above this temperature until the valve temperature setpoint is achieved.

2.9 Python Model Application

2.9.1 Weather Data

Figure 2. 12 Global horizontal irradiance map of Kenya by the World Bank Group. Homa Bay and Narok weather stations are indicated with white points (Kenya - ENERGYDATA.INFO)

As the project is expected to continue in Nakuru, it is essential to investigate the operating conditions in that region. Weather data for Narok and Homa Bay for the years 2020 and 2021 is freely available from the World Bank Group. The datasets include global horizontal irradiance and air temperature sampled every minute.

Narok serves as a good proxy for Nakuru in terms of weather data. It is located approximately 100 km away, with elevations of 1850 m for Nakuru and 1914 m for the Narok weather station. In terms of average global horizontal irradiation, Narok records a higher value of 6.5 kWh/m²/day compared to Nakuru's 5.9 kWh/m²/day. For context, Nairobi averages 5.3 kWh/m²/day (see Figure 2. 12).

Homa Bay, despite being 220 km away and situated at an altitude of 1335 m, also shows an average global horizontal irradiation of 5.9 kWh/m²/day, which is equivalent to Nakuru (see Figure 2. 12).

For further research, if deemed necessary, monthly weather data for Nakuru can be obtained from the Kenyan Meteorological Department for a fee of 600 Kenyan shillings per year per parameter (yielding 12 data points for 600 Ksh).

Global horizontal irradiance data will be utilized to run the model, providing a good approximation given that the locations considered are near the equator, resulting in a near 0° tilt angle for the solar collectors.

2.9.2 Model Analysis

In the existing model, the valve temperature is set at 78 °C, which aligns with the design setpoint of the current thermostat valve. The main tank has a capacity of 150 liters, and the heat exchanger is given an efficiency of 60 %. Given that the portion of the main tank discharged during each cycle is unknown, we use a standard value of 0.5 for this parameter.

The first step in the analysis is to identify the months with the least productivity for both Narok and Homa Bay, characterized by the lowest observed irradiation levels. These months represent the periods when it would be most challenging to meet the energy demands for the effluent flow. Conversely, we will also identify the months with the highest productivity for both locations.

For Narok and Homa Bay, July 2021 emerges as the weakest month, while March 2021 stands out as the strongest. These two months will be the focus of our analysis, as the goal is to ensure that the pasteurizer operates effectively throughout the year.

During the simulation, several parameters will be varied to assess their impact on system performance.

- The efficiency of the heat exchanger e will be varied from 30 % to 80 %.
- The main tank capacity MTC will be adjusted between 100 liters and 360 liters, reflecting the smallest and largest models available in the Seven Stars Solar water heaters catalogue.
- The valve temperature setpoint T^{valve} will be varied from 70 °C to 82 °C.
- The value of the discharge portion x will be explored in the range of 0.2 to 0.99.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 E.coli Concentration

During the months of June to August in Nairobi, the solar pasteurizer failed to achieve the necessary temperature of 78 °C for the thermostat valve to open. As a result, the system was unable to process the desired daily volume of sludge under these weather conditions. Consequently, only sample types 1, 2 and 5 from section **Error! Reference source not found.** are collected for analysis. These are the raw effluent, semi-treated effluent, and fully-processed effluent (leak), which is a drip sample due to the thermostat valve not achieving a perfect seal.

Table 3. 1 E.coli concentrations for samples taken on different dates in 2024

Collection Date	Raw Sludge ($\frac{\text{cfu}}{100 \text{ mL}}$)	Semi-Treated Sludge ($\frac{\text{cfu}}{100 \text{ mL}}$)	Fully-Processed (leak) Sludge ($\frac{\text{cfu}}{100 \text{ mL}}$)
June 30 th	71200	>200	No sample
July 1 st	41600	>200	>200
July 24 th	112200	900	3370
August 29 th	315000	8000	400

Despite the insufficient sunlight irradiance, the results from the membrane filtration show a marked decrease in E.coli concentration that can be attributed to the pasteurizer. Table 3. 1 shows a log-2 reduction in concentration from raw sludge to semi-treated sludge. This outcome is expected, as even though the temperature of 78 °C was not reached inside the main tank, the sludge was still maintained at lower pasteurization temperatures for an extended holding time, allowing for effective pasteurization.

Interestingly, in the samples from the 24th of July on Table 3. 1, the fully-processed sludge from the leak in the thermostat valve has a 3.74 times higher E.coli concentration than the sludge inside the main tank. This observation may suggest evidence of regrowth. The sludge leaking from the valve flows through the heat exchanger, where the bottom half must fill before the sludge can drip out of the final outlet for sampling. During the time it takes for the sludge to flow out of the heat exchanger, it is no longer being heated.

Currently, the heat exchanger is positioned horizontally to maximize contact time and heat exchange. However, this configuration introduces the risk of stagnant pasteurized effluent, which can promote bacterial regrowth and biofilm formation. To mitigate these risks, it is essential to avoid allowing stagnant treated effluent to remain in the heat exchanger after a period of flow.

Therefore, the heat exchanger should be inclined downward to facilitate complete drainage of runoff.

Furthermore, concrete drying beds such as the ones used in Raini Primary School will accumulate moisture during rainfall events, providing the conditions conducive to regrowth (Zaleski et al., 2005). Instead, it is recommended to dispose of the treated effluent in soils enriched with indigenous microbes, which can provide biotic competition against any remaining fecal pathogens.

3.2 Impact of the Convection Loop

3.2.1 Effectiveness

Figure 3. 1 Temperature and light data from 18th to 19th of May

Figure 3. 1 illustrates the temperature mismatch between the sludge in the main tank and that in the PPR outlet during the week prior to implementation of the convection loop. This discrepancy can reach up to 15 °C and occurs due to stagnation of the sludge at the outlet, leading to heat loss. This situation is problematic because the temperature control system depends on accurately assessing the temperature in the main tank, which is compromised if the proximal effluent is not at the same temperature.

Figure 3. 2 Temperature data from 29th to 31st of May

In contrast, Figure 3. 2 demonstrates the effects of the convection loop one week after implementation. The temperature at the outlet now closely follows the temperature of the main tank, indicating that circulation has significantly improved.

3.2.2 Behavior Concerns - Thermostat valve

Figure 3. 3 Illustration of flow reversal in the convection loop once the valve opens

Under a model utilizing the thermostat valve for temperature control along with a convection loop, an undesirable scenario can arise.

The left diagram of Figure 3. 3 illustrates the flows occurring in the main tank and the convection loop above it while the sludge is heating up. The right diagram of Figure 3. 3 depicts what can happen once the valve temperature setpoint is reached and the valve opens. The sludge discharging from the valve could disrupt the convection loop: a rapid flow from the main tank to the valve may create a suction or aspiration effect, causing the convection loop to flow in the wrong direction.

Duff & Hodgson, (2005a) employ a convection loop with a riser pipe for temperature control, which mitigates this issue. In their system, the flow from the riser pipe is low-pressure, insufficient to induce aspiration.

This concern is especially critical if the convection loop feeds back into the raw effluent inlet of the main tank. In this scenario, the aspiration effect could inadvertently draw untreated effluent through the valve, completely bypassing the solar water heater.

To eliminate this risk, a check valve can be installed in the convection loop. However, this solution may lead to increased pressure losses and potentially inhibit convection within the loop.

3.3 System Cost

Table 3. 2 Cost of each component for the solar pasteurizer in Kenyan Shillings and US Dollars

Solar Water Heater	Heat Exchanger	Thermostat Valve	Piping Elements	Total
45000 ksh	4850 ksh	3000 ksh	7500 ksh	60350 ksh
348 usd	37.5 usd	23.2 usd	58 usd	467 usd

The total cost of the solar pasteurizer, as detailed in Table 3. 2, amount to 60350 Kenyan shillings or around 467 USD. In comparison, the current post-treatment solution at Raini Primary School – gravel filtration beds – costs around 2000 USD for the 500 students.

This indicates that the solar pasteurizer is over four times more economical, presenting a compelling financial incentive for its implementation in additional ADs. Furthermore, this cost efficiency leaves room for potential enhancements to the system, which is still in its prototyping stage.

Notably, the solar water heater constitutes 75 % of the total cost. The model selected is the most affordable off-the-shelf option, featuring the lowest capacity available.

3.4 Model Results

3.4.1 Volume of Pasteurized Flow

Simulating the operation of the solar pasteurizer during the least productive months for Narok and Homa Bay reveals that, unlike the temperature curves observed at Raini Primary School, the solar pasteurizers in these locations take only two days to reach the designed valve temperature setpoint of 78 °C from ambient conditions. This finding underscores that both sites receive significantly more solar irradiance than Raini, where the simulation was unable to achieve the valve temperature setpoint.

Figure 3. 4 Temperature Simulation of a solar pasteurizer in Narok in July 2021

The peaks in Figure 3. 4 indicate when the sludge reaches the temperature at which the valve opens, followed by a reset to a lower temperature as hot sludge is discharged and preheated sludge enters the system. The data reveals a series of peaks separated by dips in temperature during the night.

Under the standard parameters outlined in section 2.9.2, Narok yields an average daily volume of sludge of 89 l/day/m² in July 2021, having reached the valve temperature setpoint 58 times during that month. Homa Bay yields an average daily volume of 86.5 l/day/m², achieving the valve temperature setpoint 56 times in the same period.

For a school like Raini, which has 500 students, the volume of pasteurized sludge must exceed 200 liters per day. This requirement can be met with a surface collector area of 2.3 m². Considering the spacing of the vacuum heating tubes, this corresponds to an effective collector area of approximately 3.5 m² (see Annex 2).

3.4.2 Holding Time

In the model, the holding time is defined as the duration, measured in minutes, that a batch of sludge remains above 72 °C. This temperature was selected based on the shoulder observed in the zone corresponding to at least 90 % reduction, as defined by Espinosa et al., (2020). This shoulder, which can be seen in Figure 1. 1, may be attributed to the melting temperature of viral capsids. By choosing 72 °C as the pasteurization temperature, we leverage the biological vulnerability of certain bacteria, thereby reducing the required holding time.

In Figure 3. 4, the holding time is represented by red markers. For instance, on July 3rd, we observe that the holding time is interrupted by nighttime temperature dips below 72 °C, resuming on July 4th. Due to these longer holding times, particularly at the end of the day, a median holding time is employed instead of an average to convey results more accurately.

While the volume of pasteurized sludge becomes a limiting factor during the winter months, the holding time presents a limitation during summer months when solar irradiance is high. This is due to the faster heating of the sludge, resulting in reduced pasteurization duration.

Under the standard parameters outlined in section 2.9.2, the median holding time for Narok in March 2021 is 52 minutes, with a minimum of 41 minutes. For Homa Bay, the median holding time in March 2021 is 57 minutes, with a minimum of 42 minutes.

At 72 °C, for the zone of at least 90 % reduction in pathogens (see Table 1. 1), 79 minutes of holding time are prescribed. Conversely, achieving a zone of at least 99.9 % reduction necessitates a holding time of 2718 minutes, which is simply unattainable for the solar pasteurizer. Consequently, efforts should focus on validating the zone of at least 90 % reduction in pathogens.

3.4.3 Parameter Analysis

Given that the volume of pasteurized effluent is the limiting factor during winter months while the holding time becomes the limiting factor in summer, it is logical to plot each metric in their respective "weak" months to assess the necessary improvements in both areas.

The blue scatter plot indicates the average processed volume of sludge in l/day/m² for July 2021, with varying parameters. The red scatter plot represents the median holding time in minutes for March 2021, also with varying parameters.

Figure 3. 5 Processed Volume and Holding Time for varying Valve Temperature Setpoint

As the temperature setpoint increases, more energy and time are required to heat the sludge until the valve opens, resulting in a decrease in the volume of sludge processed. However, this increase in temperature significantly enhances the holding time. For the tested parameters,

Figure 3. 5 indicates that the system meets the holding time requirement only when the valve temperature setpoint exceeds 80 °C.

Figure 3. 6 Processed Volume and Holding Time for varying Heat Exchanger Efficiency

As the efficiency of the heat exchanger increases, the preheated sludge enters the main tank at a higher temperature, resulting in an exponential increase in the volume of sludge processed. Concurrently, the energy requirements – and thus the holding time – decrease.

Figure 3. 6 illustrates that the holding time is not consistently achieved under these parameters.

Figure 3. 7 Processed Volume and Holding Time for varying Main Tank Capacity

As the main tank capacity increases, the processed volume rises only slightly due to a reduction in temperature losses. This occurs because the volume increases at a faster rate than the surface

area of the tank, resulting in a heat capacity that increases more rapidly than the overall heat transfer coefficient with ambient air. The number of heating tubes correlates with the main tank capacity (see Annex 2), meaning that the daily processed volume increases in proportion to the tank's capacity, while remaining relatively stable when normalized by the collector surface area. The holding time is relatively unaffected by main tank capacity, and Figure 3. 7 shows that the required holding time is not respected.

Figure 3. 8 Temperature Simulation of a solar pasteurizer in Narok in July 2021 with high x

Figure 3. 8 illustrates the effect that the discharge factor x can have on pasteurization dynamics; in it the simulation of

Figure 3. 4 is repeated, with a discharge factor x increased to 0.9. With only 10 % of the sludge in the main tank is discharged when the valve is opened, the reset temperature remains close to the valve temperature setpoint. This results in a significantly more homogeneous flow characterized by smaller batches processed over shorter time intervals. A similar effect is observed when the heat exchanger achieves a high efficiency value.

Figure 3.9 Processed Volume and Holding Time for varying Discharge Portion x

As the discharge factor x increases, the volume of each batch of sludge becomes smaller, resulting in reduced energy requirements for heating. Consequently, the holding time decreases. However, this also allows for the processing of more batches of smaller volume. Overall, the total processed volume tends to decline, as the decrease in batch volume outpaces the increase in processing frequency. In Figure 3.9, the holding time does not meet the target requirements.

One of the model's assumptions is that the discharge of sludge occurs instantaneously when the valve opens. In reality, this discharge takes several minutes, with smaller values of x resulting in longer discharge times compared to larger values. Therefore, the overall impact of x on processed volume may be less significant than what Figure 3.9 suggests.

The flat trajectory of the holding time plot at the beginning of the increases in heat exchanger efficiency and x is merely a result of how the model measures holding time, based on the pasteurization temperature set at 72 °C. This does not affect the physical dynamics of the model. At low heat exchanger efficiencies and low x values, the temperature to which the main tank resets after discharge remains below 72 °C. The transition from a flat to a downward-sloping plot occurs when efficiency and x reach sufficient levels for the main tank to reset at 72 °C.

Most of these dynamics can be understood by examining the operation of the solar pasteurizer. Notably, the influence of various parameters on the volume of processed effluent per day differs significantly. The main tank capacity serves as the strongest lever, as it directly correlates with an increase in collector surface area. In contrast, the heat exchanger efficiency has a less pronounced effect, while the temperature setpoint and factor x exert only marginal influences. When it comes to holding time, the thermostat temperature setpoint emerges as the most significant factor (

Figure 3. 5), as the impact of the heat exchanger efficiency and x can be dampened if their values are not too high.

3.4.4 Operation under Ideal Parameters

A desired configuration for the parameters would involve increasing the main tank capacity to 240 liters, which is the smallest capacity that can yield an average daily processed sludge volume exceeding 200 liters. To enhance holding time, the valve temperature setpoint should be maintained as high as possible. The discharge portion x should remain low unless flow homogeneity is a desired characteristic. There exists a threshold for heat exchanger efficiency that should not be surpassed to maintain a reasonable holding time; however, it is yet to be determined if the efficiency approaches that threshold.

The following simulations illustrate the operation of the pasteurizer under improved parameter values, under the most and least sunny conditions (see Annex 3):

$$T^{valve} = 82 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \quad e = 70 \% \quad x = 0.5 \quad MTC = 240 \text{ litres}$$

The volume of processed effluent is assessed using irradiance data for Homa Bay in July 2020 (see Annex Figure 1), which reflects the lowest irradiance levels and, consequently, the lowest processed volume. The average daily processed sludge is 205 liters (82 liters/m²), surpassing the target value of 200 liters largely due to the 60 % increase in main tank capacity.

The holding time is evaluated using irradiance data for Narok in March 2021 (see Annex Figure 2), representing the highest irradiance levels and, therefore, the shortest holding times. The median holding time is 91 minutes, with a minimum of 67 minutes. While this aligns with the Feachem et al. safety zone, the minimum falls short of the revised threshold for at least a 90 % reduction in pathogens. By reducing the heat exchanger efficiency, we can sacrifice some volume of pasteurized effluent in exchange for longer holding times. For instance, decreasing the heat exchanger efficiency from 70 % to 65 % (see Annex Figure 3) increases the median holding time to 87 minutes, with a minimum of 69 minutes. This adjustment is sensible in Narok, where abundant sunlight makes it easy to achieve the required processed volume.

The resulting values (102 liters/day/m², with a median holding time of 87 minutes at 72 °C) can be compared to similar systems designed for pasteurizing drinking water in developing countries. For instance, Duff & Hodgson, (2005b) report a yield of 192 liters/m² for a sunny day, using a density-driven system (riser pipe) set for 80 °C spillover. Koninck et al., (2024) achieve pasteurization of 370 liters/day/m² at a temperature of 68 °C, utilizing an AVTA Danfoss thermostatic valve and plate heat exchanger. They also implement a convection loop with a non-return valve to homogenize effluent temperatures. The high productivity in this system is facilitated by the efficient heat exchanger and lower pasteurization temperature.

The model results are consistent with the order of magnitude observed in existing systems.

3.4.5 Limitations of the Model

The results drawn from this model are qualitative and quantitative. More attention should be given to the qualitative results. While the accuracy of the model remains unverified, the trends it outlines can be regarded as valid and beneficial for designing a system that meets sanitation requirements.

Koninck et al., (2024) develop a more comprehensive model that employs nodal discretization of the solar pasteurizer into distinct components, which allows for the inclusion of mass flow rates. This model also incorporates bacterial inactivation dynamics by correlating time-temperature curves with pathogen inactivation curves. Additionally, it takes into account the mechanics of the thermostat valve at various temperatures and the flow it permits.

While extensive data collection would be necessary to parameterize such an advanced model, in the later commercial phases of the project, having a detailed model would be helpful for accurately dimensioning system components. This model would facilitate precise and automatic calculations of the necessary parameters to meet the specific requirements of the plant as it scales.

3.5 Degradation of Components

Figure 3. 10 Inside of vacuum tubes before (top) and after (bottom) being rinsed with water

The effect of sludge exposure 45 days after initial installation was assessed. During the maintenance procedure, sediment deposits were observed on the bottom surfaces of the vacuum heating tubes after their removal from the main tank. As illustrated in Figure 3. 10, a simple rinse with water effectively cleared away these deposits. Additionally, a comparison of the irradiance and temperature curves from the beginning of the installation to just before maintenance showed no significant evidence of fouling within the tubes, indicating that the deposits were not substantial enough to impair the heating efficiency of the system.

Figure 3. 11 Sacrificial anode rod before (top) and after (bottom) exposure to sludge

Figure 3. 11 reveals significant corrosion on the sacrificial anode rod after 45 days of exposure. The rod, composed of magnesium (Mg), is particularly suitable for soft water due to its susceptibility to corrosion. Magnesium oxidation occurs via the release of two electrons:

Equation 3. 1

It is suspected that hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is a primary contributor to the corrosion of the rod. H₂S exhibits a highly aggressive corrosion mechanism, capable of generating sulfuric acid and hydrogen atoms when reacting with water (Sotoodeh, 2021). In AD effluent, H₂S is produced through the reduction of sulfate ions by sulfate-reducing bacteria (Vu et al., 2022):

Equation 3. 2

As shown in Equation 3. 2, this reduction requires 8 negative electrons, which can be provided by the oxidation of a metal. Thus, the corrosion of magnesium through Equation 3. 1 which releases two electrons, can contribute to the formation of additional H₂S.

The degradation rate of the anode is likely to accelerate during normal pasteurizer operation, as the circulation of fresh sludge will continuously replenish the reactants, enhancing the chemical reactions.

This study did not evaluate the impact of sludge exposure on the copper pipe within the heat exchanger or the thermostat valve in the outlet block. As these components are not in close proximity to the sacrificial anode, it is crucial for future projects to assess their resilience against operation with AD sludge.

3.6 Improved Solar Pasteurizer

Figure 3. 12 Cut Illustration of the Improved Solar Pasteurizer

This hypothetical concept aims to overcome the limitations of the existing solar pasteurizer, particularly regarding the corrosive nature of fecal sludge. The new design incorporates additional components, including a low-pressure check valve, traversing copper tubes, and copper T-connectors.

Unlike the existing solar pasteurizer, this system does not have effluent flowing directly in the solar water heater and vacuum tubes, as this has proved to exhibit degradation of parts over time (Degradation of Components). Instead, as seen in Figure 3. 12, water is used as a working fluid in the solar water heater - which is now a closed loop - and this water is used to heat the copper tubes that the sludge travels through. This is designed to ease the maintenance needs of the system.

Straight copper tubes will be installed inside the main tank, fully traversing it as depicted by the orange pipes in Figure 3. 12. PPR pipes at the end of the tubes connect them to one another. The sludge flows through these copper tubes and is heated by the water in the main tank. Figure 3. 12 only shows 2 copper traversing tubes, however the real design should incorporate many more. This arrangement effectively transforms the main tank into a tube-in-shell heat exchanger, with water in the shell (main tank) and sludge flowing through the copper tubes. By disassembling the PPR connections on the outside of the main tank, the copper tubes can easily be accessed and cleaned.

Additionally, this design allows the pasteurizer to take advantage of the antimicrobial properties of copper. Sizirici et al., (2024) found that a 94 minute contact time with copper by itself could lead to a log-2 or log-3 reduction in E.coli. The vacuum heating tubes, made from a copper alloy, may also contribute to E.coli reduction after prolonged exposure. However, concerns about copper leaching in the effluent have been raised. The study concluded that the amount of copper ions dissolved in the water does not compromise the quality of the drinking water produced. For AD sludge, the risk is lower since pasteurized sludge is not intended for direct consumption.

Nonetheless, because the corrosiveness of the AD sludge remains unexamined, conducting a copper-leaching analysis could be beneficial to ensure no intervention is needed.

In this setup, the discharge factor x is particularly important, as the traversing tubes limit turbulent flow when the valve opens. This restriction reduces the mixing between hot sludge in the main tank and incoming cold sludge, allowing x to represent the volume fraction of the main tank occupied by the traversing tubes.

The outlet block is positioned at the end of the last traversing tube, with the thermostatic valve oriented downward and the convection loop directed upward. This convection loop will include a check valve, reintroducing fluid back at the level of the PPR pipe connecting the first two copper traversing tubes.

(Duff & Hodgson, 2005b) note the challenges associated with thermostatic valves as temperature control devices. These valves typically open and close gradually as they approach their setpoint, which can result in a slow response to temperature changes. Such delays may lead to unstable flow during the warming-up phase at the beginning of the day, potentially causing underpasteurized sludge to exit the system. This issue requires further study to assess the associated risks and hazards, reinforcing the decision to utilize a thermostatic valve with a higher temperature setpoint – such as an 82 °C standard thermostat valve for potential safety buffer – to enhance holding time and overall effectiveness of the pasteurization process.

Figure 3.13 Cut Illustration of the Improved Heat Exchanger (center) and Current Heat Exchanger (right corner)

On the other side of the thermostatic valve, both the heat exchanger and the PPR pipe leading to it should be sloped downward to prevent stagnation and regrowth.

The heat exchanger can be improved by replacing the PPR T-connectors (seen in green in the top-right illustration of Figure 3. 13) with copper T-connectors (seen in orange in Figure 3. 13). These copper connectors can be welded to the copper tubes using the appropriate reducers, effectively eliminating the risk of leaks from the heat exchanger. This modification would facilitate the flow of hot pasteurized effluent through the tube, ultimately improving overall heat transfer by minimizing heat loss to the ambient air surrounding the shell.

4 Conclusions and Recommendations

The current solar pasteurizer has not yet achieved effective sludge processing, primarily because the thermostat valve's opening temperature has not been reached during the low irradiance winter months near Nairobi. The study confirms that the most suitable temperature control mechanism for pasteurizing AD sludge is the thermostatic valve. While the system can achieve log-2 reductions in E.coli concentrations at low temperatures, this is insufficient to prevent bacterial regrowth in the heat exchanger when sludge becomes stagnant. For the system to operate effectively during winter in Nairobi, it is recommended to lower the valve's temperature setpoint to 65 °C and to conduct further validation through bacteriological analysis.

The model developed from data collected on the solar pasteurizer system offers valuable insights into how different parameters influence its operation. A key observation is that the productivity of the solar pasteurizer is inversely related to the holding time of pasteurization. Therefore, in regions with low sunlight, efforts should focus on enhancing productivity, while in areas with abundant sunlight, the emphasis should shift towards increasing holding time. To boost holding time, this study suggests setting a higher temperature setpoint on the thermostatic valve, whereas increasing the solar collector area will directly enhance productivity.

The total cost of materials for the solar pasteurizer system is approximately 467 USD. This represents a significant improvement over the previously used gravel filtration bed and allows for financial flexibility to enhance the system further. Increasing either the solar collector area, or main tank capacity, would greatly impact overall cost.

Finally, an improved conceptual design for the solar pasteurizer is proposed to tackle issues of system degradation. This design utilizes water as a heating fluid to pasteurize sludge within traversing copper tubes, potentially enhancing both efficiency and durability.

Bibliography

- Carielo da Silva, G., Tiba, C., & Calazans, G. M. T. (2016). Solar pasteurizer for the microbiological decontamination of water. *Renewable Energy*, *87*, 711–719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2015.11.012>
- Dobrowsky, P. H., Carstens, M., De Villiers, J., Cloete, T. E., & Khan, W. (2015). Efficiency of a closed-coupled solar pasteurization system in treating roof harvested rainwater. *Science of The Total Environment*, *536*, 206–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.06.126>
- Duff, W. S., & Hodgson, D. A. (2005a). A simple high efficiency solar water purification system. *Solar Energy*, *79*(1), 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2004.10.005>
- Espinosa, M. F., Sancho, A. N., Mendoza, L. M., Mota, C. R., & Verbyla, M. E. (2020). Systematic review and meta-analysis of time-temperature pathogen inactivation. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, *230*, 113595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113595>
- Feachem, R. G., Bradley, D. J., Garelick, H., & Mara, D. D. (1981). *Appropriate Technology for Water Supply and Sanitation*.
- Kenya—Solar Radiation Measurement Data—ENERGYDATA.INFO. (n.d.). Retrieved October 10, 2024, from <https://energydata.info/dataset/kenya-solar-radiation-measurement-data>
- Koninck, C., Stitou, D., Mancaux, J.-M., & Goetz, V. (2024). A passive continuous flow process for solar pasteurisation of river water. Part II: Modelling and outdoor experiments for performance characterizations. *Solar Energy*, *279*, 112841. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2024.112841>
- Labatut, R. A., Angenent, L. T., & Scott, N. R. (2014). Conventional mesophilic vs. thermophilic anaerobic digestion: A trade-off between performance and stability? *Water Research*, *53*, 249–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2014.01.035>
- Owamah, H. I., Dahunsi, S. O., Oranusi, U. S., & Alfa, M. I. (2014). Fertilizer and sanitary quality of digestate biofertilizer from the co-digestion of food waste and human excreta. *Waste Management*, *34*(4), 747–752. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2014.01.017>
- Reith, J. H., & Wijffels, R. H. (2003). *Bio-methane & bio-hydrogen: Status and perspectives of biological methane and hydrogen production*. Dutch Biological Hydrogen Foundation.
- Sizirici, B., Rachid, E., & Eniola, J. O. (2024). Assessing passive thermosiphon solar water heater as low-cost, sustainable water disinfection technology: Leveraging the Germicidal effect of copper and thermal convection loops. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, *12*(2), 112475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2024.112475>

- Sotoodeh, K. (2021). Chapter Twelve—Material selection and corrosion. In K. Sotoodeh (Ed.), *Subsea Valves and Actuators for the Oil and Gas Industry* (pp. 421–457). Gulf Professional Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-90605-0.00004-9>
- Vu, H. P., Nguyen, L. N., Wang, Q., Ngo, H. H., Liu, Q., Zhang, X., & Nghiem, L. D. (2022). Hydrogen sulphide management in anaerobic digestion: A critical review on input control, process regulation, and post-treatment. *Bioresource Technology*, *346*, 126634. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2021.126634>
- Wang, M., Ateia, M., Awfa, D., & Yoshimura, C. (2021). Regrowth of bacteria after light-based disinfection—What we know and where we go from here. *Chemosphere*, *268*, 128850. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.128850>
- WHO/UNICEF Joint Programme for Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene (JMP). (2023). *PROGRESS ON HOUSEHOLD DRINKING WATER, SANITATION AND HYGIENE 2000-2022: Special focus on gender*.
- Winker, M., Vinnerås, B., Muskolus, A., Arnold, U., & Clemens, J. (2009). Fertiliser products from new sanitation systems: Their potential values and risks. *Bioresource Technology*, *100*(18), 4090–4096. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2009.03.024>
- Zaleski, K. J., Josephson, K. L., Gerba, C. P., & Pepper, I. L. (2005). Potential Regrowth and Recolonization of Salmonellae and Indicators in Biosolids and Biosolid-Amended Soil. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, *71*(7), 3701–3708. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.71.7.3701-3708.2005>

Annex

Annex 1

Water density at 20 °C = 998.2 kg/m³

Water density at 70 °C = 977 kg/m³

Using Bernoulli's principle:

$$P_{atm} + \rho g z = Constant$$

Annex Equation 1

Applying Annex Equation 1 to the top of the columns of water in the pasteurizer, one which is in the AD at 20 °C and the other which is at the top of the riser pipe outlet at 70 °C, we can find the following equivalence:

$$\rightarrow P_{atm} + \rho_{20} g z_{20} = P_{atm} + \rho_{70} g z_{70}$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{\rho_{20}}{\rho_{70}} = \frac{z_{70}}{z_{20}}$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{z_{70}}{z_{20}} = 1.0215$$

With P_{atm} as atmospheric pressure, g the gravitational acceleration, ρ_{20} and ρ_{70} the water densities at 20 °C and 70 °C respectively, z_{20} and z_{70} the height of the water columns at 20 °C and 70 °C respectively.

Given that the outlet of the AD positioned at $z_{20} = 96.5$ cm above the bottom of the main tank:

$$\rightarrow z_{70} = 98.5 \text{ cm}$$

Annex 2

Annex Table 1 Seven Stars Solar Low-Pressure Vacuum Tube Water Heater Models

Main Tank Capacity	Tank Size (diameter and length)	Tube Quantity	Tube Size (diameter and length)	Solar Collector Area (Annex Equation 2)	Effective Area (Annex Equation 3)
100 liters	D _{out} = 455 mm L _{out} = 965 mm	10	D = 58 mm L = 1800 mm	S = 1.04 m ²	S _{eff} = 1.74 m ²
150 liters	D _{out} = 455 mm L _{out} = 1360 mm	15	D = 58 mm L = 1800 mm	S = 1.57 m ²	S _{eff} = 2.45 m ²
200 liters	D _{out} = 455 mm L _{out} = 1740 mm	20	D = 58 mm L = 1800 mm	S = 2.09 m ²	S _{eff} = 3.13 m ²
240 liters	D _{out} = 455 mm L _{out} = 2080 mm	24	D = 58 mm L = 1800 mm	S = 2.51 m ²	S _{eff} = 3.74 m ²
300 liters	D _{out} = 455 mm L _{out} = 2560 mm	30	D = 58 mm L = 1800 mm	S = 3.13 m ²	S _{eff} = 4.61 m ²
360 liters	D _{out} = 455 mm L _{out} = 3040 mm	36	D = 58 mm L = 1800 mm	S = 3.76 m ²	S _{eff} = 5.47 m ²

Solar Collector Surface Area:

$$S = N_{tube} \cdot D_{tube} \cdot L_{tube}$$

Annex Equation 2

Where S is the cumulative surface area of the solar collector vacuum heating tubes in m². N_{tube} is the quantity heating tubes on the system, D_{tube} is the diameter of the tube in meters, and L_{tube} is the length of the tube in meters.

Solar Collector Effective Surface Area:

$$S_{eff} = L_{tube} \cdot MTL$$

Annex Equation 3

Where S_{eff} is the effective surface area of the solar collector, including the spacing between the tubes, in m². L_{tube} is the length of the tube in meters, and MTL is the length of the main tank in meters.

Main Tank Heat Loss Surface Area:

The main tank is a cylinder. The listed diameter and lengths in Annex Table 1 are the outside dimensions of the tank. Therefore, to obtain the surface area for heat exchange, the thickness of its walls must be intuited using the listed main tank capacity.

A probable thickness for the main tank walls is 27.5 mm for the circular part of the cylinder, and 75 mm for the caps which close the cylinder. This results in inner diameter of:

$$D_{in} = D_{out} - 55 = 455 - 55 = 400 \text{ mm}$$

Annex Equation 4

The inner length is:

$$L_{in} = L_{out} - 150 \text{ mm}$$

From this, the approximate rule of thumb is established that the inner length of the tank is:

$$L_{in}^* = 8.1 \cdot MTC$$

Annex Equation 5

Where L_{in}^* is the approximated inner length of the tank in millimeters, and MTC is the main tank capacity in liters.

$$error = \frac{|L_{in}^* - L_{in}|}{L_{in}}$$

The approximation of Annex Equation 5 results in a maximum *error* of 1.9% for the instance where $MTC = 200$ liters.

Therefore, combining Annex Equation 4 with Annex Equation 5, we get the Main tank heat loss surface area, A in mm^2 :

$$A = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \left(\frac{D_{in}}{2}\right)^2 + \pi \cdot D_{in} \cdot L_{in}^* \text{ mm}^2$$

$$\rightarrow A = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \left(\frac{D_{in}}{2}\right)^2 + \pi \cdot D_{in} \cdot 8.1 \cdot MTC \text{ mm}^2$$

Annex Equation 6

This Annex Equation 6 is the formula used in the python model to calculate temperature losses to the ambient air.

Annex 3

Annex Figure 1 Simulated pasteurizer operation under ideal parameters of section 3.4.4 for Homa Bay in July 2020

55 batches of sludge were pasteurized. The average daily processed volume is 212 l/day, or 84 l/day/m². The median holding time is 173 minutes and the minimum holding time is 69 minutes.

Annex Figure 2 Simulated pasteurizer operation under ideal parameters of section 3.4.4 for Narok in March 2021

126 batches of sludge were pasteurized. The average daily processed volume is 488 l/day, or 195 l/day/m². The median holding time is 74 minutes and the minimum holding time is 57 minutes.

Annex Figure 3 Simulated pasteurizer operation under ideal parameters of section 3.4.4 for Narok in March 2021, with heat exchanger efficiency lowered to 65 %

110 batches of sludge were pasteurized. The average daily processed volume is 426 l/day, or 170 l/day/m². The median holding time is 86.5 minutes and the minimum holding time is 67 minutes.